

Food Insecurity and Nutrient Deficiency as Major Determinants of Undernutrition among Tribal Preschool Children in Paschimanchal, West Bengal, India

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Abstract:

Limited access to adequate food remains a key indicator of malnutrition globally, with household food insufficiency constituting a major underlying cause of undernutrition. In India, national surveys consistently identify undernutrition as a significant public health issue among tribal preschool children, despite their rich traditional knowledge and distinctive dietary practices. In this context, the present study aimed to assess dietary and nutrient intake and examine its association with undernutrition among tribal preschool children in the Paschimanchal area of West Bengal.

A community based cross-sectional study was conducted among 1,207 children aged 1–5 years during April, 2020 to May, 2022. Anthropometric measurements were obtained using standard procedures, and dietary intake was assessed through a 24-hour recall method. The findings revealed that a high prevalence of undernutrition, with 46.6% underweight, 41.5% stunted, and 28.7% wasted, according to WHO criteria. Diets were predominantly cereal-based, with relatively adequate intake of roots, tubers, and sugar, but low consumption of milk, fruits, and other essential food groups. Nutrient analysis showed that intakes of fat, calcium, carotene, and vitamin B12 were below 50% of the recommended dietary allowance, while most other nutrients except carbohydrates and protein were also inadequate.

Significant associations were observed between dietary factors and nutritional outcomes. Undernutrition was associated with both food group and nutrient intake, indicating the multifactorial nature of the problem. Overall, the high burden of stunting and underweight reflects both chronic and acute nutritional deprivation. Addressing this issue requires not only improving access to diverse and nutrient-rich diets but also there is felt to enhance maternal awareness and practices related to child nutrition.

Keywords: Undernutrition, Food insecurity, Food groups, Paschimanchal, Traditional food.

1. Introduction

In the twenty-first century, most of the state and union territories of India fall within serious categories of hunger with some experiencing moderate to alarming condition, according to the India State Hunger Index (ISHI) (1). Despite rapid economic development and implementation of various nutritional supplementation programs over the past few decades, undernutrition of preschool children in India is remain a persistent public health problem (2).

Children under the age of five are the most vulnerable in any community and their nutritional status is a responsive indicator of any country's overall health and development (3).

Diet is the fundamental determinant of good health and nutritional status. Undernutrition among children is driven by multiple interrelated factors, including food insecurity, inadequate caregiver knowledge regarding appropriate child feeding practices, poor quality of supplementary foods, and a high burden of gastrointestinal and parasitic infections (4). Among these, food insecurity remains a critical contributor to undernutrition globally (5). Adequate intake of food and essential nutrients supports optimal growth, body composition, and immune function; conversely, insufficient nutrient intake leads to undernutrition and increases susceptibility to a range of diseases (6–7).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study area

Three community development blocks (Ranibandh, Bandwan and Garhbeta II) have been selected from three districts (Bankura, Purulia and Paschim Medinipur) of Paschimanchal area, West Bengal, based on tribal concentrated of the block. This region consists of 74 blocks of 7 districts in the western part of South Bengal. These 74 blocks are 16 in Bankura, 10 in Paschim Medinipur, 8 in Jhargram, 20 in Purulia, 10 in Birbhum, 8 in Paschim Burdwan and 2 in Purba Burdwan.

2.2. Study Subjects

To carry out the research work, the information has collected from tribal household having children aged 1-5 years old tribal pre-school children of Paschimanchal region in West Bengal. All information was collected by door-to-door visits through pretested questionnaire in this Paschimanchal area on April, 2020 to May, 2022.

2.3. Sampling and sample size

The subjects were selected through Multistage Cluster Sampling Method. At first Paschimanchal divided into three clusters, Bankura, Purulia and Paschim Medinipore and selected one community development block (Based on density of ST population) from each district. Then select 2-3 villages from every gram panchayat from each community development block.

Minimum estimated sample size was 1174 calculated using by standard formula ($n = z^2 pq/d^2$), (8). The calculation was made based on prevalence (p) of stunting (34%) of rural West Bengal, under five years children according to NFSH-4 (9) with desired precision (d) of $\pm 3\%$. Where, $q=100-p$ and $z=2.17$ at 98.5% confidence interval. Therefore, a total of 1174 subjects would be required to answer the research questions.

2.4. Ethical consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from the Raja Narenrda Lal Khan Women's College (Autonomous) Institutional Ethical Committee vide memo IEC/ICMR/02/IEC-ICMR/RNLKWC/2019. The purpose of the study was thoroughly explained and written consents were obtained from the parents/guardians of the children.

2.5. Statistical analysis

After taking measurements and collecting information in a particular pre-designed questioner schedule data were typing, double checking, cleaning and analyses were done of nutritional status using WHO Anthro; mean and regression using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences, 16. versions) and t-test, ANOVA using MedCalc software. Report writing was done using MS Word 2007 software.

2.6. Measurement of dietary consumption

The 24-hour recall method was employed to measure nutritional consumption. The semi-quantitative food frequencies questionnaire approach (10) was used to quantify the consumption of common foods and to reduce common sources of error, which increased the dependability of this method. Rice, which is often eaten boiled, or wheat, which is typically consumed in the form of chapattis, which are handmade flatbreads made of whole-wheat flour, are the two main grains eaten in this region. These ranged in size from household to household. The size variation of this food item provides significant sources of inaccuracy into diet surveys. In order to measure intake, samples of varied sizes were shown to each responder. With dal, curries, veggies, or sugar, these breads are eaten. By asking respondents to select one of three bowls of equal size, the amounts of these were evaluated. Respondents similarly selected glasses and standard

serving spoons that best matched their predicted consumption of rice, drinks, and other meals. This procedure helped in minimizing the errors due to variability in household-to-household food portions. Energy intakes were calculated from these portions using appropriate food tables (11) and compared with recommended dietary allowances (RDA) as described by the Indian Council of Medical Research (12).

2.7. Anthropometric measurement

Height and weight of the children was measured two times and average value was recorded following standard procedure (13). Anthropometric indices of the children were namely, wasting, stunting and underweight calculated by WHO anthro software according to the WHO Growth Child standards 2006 (14). A child was classified as underweight, stunting and wasting as weight-for-age, height-for-age and weight-of-height Z-score below -2 standard deviation.

3. Results

3.1. Nutritional status

The most popular, simple, cost-effective and low time-consuming method to assess the nutritional status are the anthropometric method. In general, the nutritional status of the preschool children is assessed by z-score method such as WAZ, HAZ, WHZ etc.

Overall, the occurrence of underweight for boys and girls (age and sex combined) in present study was 46.6% with severe underweight was 10.6%. Stunting is an important parameter in measuring malnutrition. Stunting bears witness to long-term malnutrition. The overall stunting rate was very high, which is 41.5% includes severe stunting of 11.3%. Similarly, overall, the prevalence of wasting was found to be 28.7%, of which 6.4% had severe wasting.

Table 1: Nutritional status of tribal preschool children of Paschimanchal of West Bengal

Age groups (years)	n	Under-Weight (%)	Severe Underweight (%)	Stunting (%)	Severe Stunting (%)	Wasting (%)	Severe Wasting (%)
1	286	47.2	09.8	55.1	23.2	19.6	4.5
2	295	45.4	13.2	38.6	10.5	35.3	7.1
3	270	47.4	13.0	37.0	09.6	29.4	8.2
4	295	50.2	08.5	39.3	03.7	30.8	6.1
5	061	27.9	01.6	21.3	03.3	26.2	4.9
Total	1207	46.6	10.6	41.5	11.3	28.7	6.4

3.2. Food and nutrients intake status

Diet survey is another important method for assessing nutritional status. Child nutritional status depends on the intake of food and nutrients. So, below is tabulated food and nutrients intake of the children.

3.3. Mean intake of different food stuffs of the children

Present study discusses the intake of different food groups (table 2) of pre-school children aged 1-3 years and 4-5 years. It is also express, ICMR recommended RDA, the percentage of RDA intake by children and the significant difference in dietary intake of boys and girls. Intake of cereals was very high among the children of this area, while the intake of roots and tubers and sugar was also adequate. Intake of milk and fruit in their diet was very low. In addition, the intake of the rest of the food groups was also found to be quite low.

Table 2: Dietary intake (per day) of tribal preschool children of Paschamanchal of West Bengal

Food stuffs	RDA	Sex Combined		Boys		Girls		t-value
		Mean (SD)	% of RDA	Mean	% of RDA	Mean	% of RDA	
1-3 years children (n= Sex combined-851, Boys-452, Girls-399)								
Cereals (gm)	60	145.13 (31.99)	241.8 8	143.2 (30.36)	238.67	146.73 (33.71)	244.5 5	1.471
Pulses (gm)	30	5.56 (5.88)	18.53	5.33 (5.00)	17.77	5.83 (6.74)	19.43	1.238
Flesh (gm)	50	9.69 (21.77)	19.38	10.43 (22.34)	20.86	8.25 (21.10)	16.5	-1.458
Milk (ml)	500	20.75 (62.05)	4.15	21.73 (63.42)	4.35	19.65 (80.52)	3.93	-0.422
Roots and tubers (gm)	50	46.45 (17.06)	92.9	45.50 (17.46)	91	47.52 (16.55)	95.04	1.726
Green leafy vegetable (gm)	50	9.17 (11.57)	18.34	9.15 (11.89)	18.3	9.19 (11.20)	18.38	0.050 3
Other vegetable (gm)	100	21.34 (15.12)	21.34	20.80 (14.77)	20.8	21.97 (15.51)	21.97	1.126
Fruits (gm)	100	9.51 (19.29)	9.51	8.81 (18.55)	8.81	10.30 (20.10)	10.3	1.124
Sugar (gm)	15	9.82 (4.60)	65.47	9.76 (4.60)	65.07	9.89 (4.61)	65.93	0.411
Oil (gm)	25	6.17 (2.62)	24.68	6.16 (2.93)	24.64	6.18 (2.23)	24.72	0.111

4-5 years children (n=Sex combined-356, Boys-166, Girls-190)								
Cereals (gm)	120	178.09 (20.57)	148.4 1	176.93 (20.25)	147.44	179.11 (20.84)	149.2 6	0.998
Pulses (gm)	30	6.19 (5.35)	20.63	5.86 (5.24)	19.53	6.48 (5.44)	21.6	1.091
Flesh (gm)	50	15.24 (28.47)	30.48	15.78 (29.32)	31.56	14.77 (28.31)	29.54	-0.330
Milk (ml)	500	18.26 (56.82)	3.65	17.77 (56.41)	3.55	18.68 (57.33)	3.74	0.151
Roots and tubers (gm)	100	68.90 (15.32)	68.9	69.07 (15.20)	69.07	68.76 (15.47)	68.76	-0.190
Green leafy vegetable (gm)	50	17.19 (16.63)	34.38	14.88 (15.38)	29.76	19.21 (17.80)	38.42	2.438 *
Other vegetable (gm)	100	25.80 (19.19)	25.8	26.63 (18.21)	26.63	25.08 (20.03)	25.08	-0.760
Fruits (gm)	100	17.88 (26.46)	17.88	17.59 (25.25)	17.59	18.13 (27.53)	18.13	0.192
Sugar (gm)	20	11.51 (5.32)	57.55	11.51 (5.12)	57.55	11.51 (5.50)	57.55	0.000
Oil (gm)	25	7.55 (2.76)	30.2	7.40 (2.61)	29.6	7.68 (2.89)	30.72	0.954

Significant Level * $p < 0.05$

Foods requirements (ICMR), Source: Dietary Guidelines for Indian- A manual, 2011, National Institute of Nutrition, ICMR, Hyderabad.

* *One portion (30gm) of pulse may be exchange with one portion (50 gm) of egg/meat/chicken/fish*

There was no significant difference in average daily intake of various food groups between boys and girls aged one to three years. However, there was a significant ($p < 0.05$, $t = 2.438$) difference in the consumption rate of green leafy vegetable between boys and girls aged four to five years.

3.4. Average nutrient intake of tribal preschool children of Paschamanchal of West Bengal

Similarly in this study assessed the ICMR recommended daily nutrients requirements and nutrient intakes of pre-school children in the region (table 3). Here the sex combined nutrients intake, % of RDA intake and significant difference in nutrient intake of boys and girls are expressed. Intake of fat, calcium, carotene and vitamin-B₁₂ among children in this region was less than 50% of RDA. On the other hand, the rate of intake of all other nutrients except carbohydrates and proteins was also low. One to three years boys and girls, folic acid ($p < 0.001$, $t = 4.190$) and 4-5 years girls and boys, iron ($p < 0.05$, $t = 2.281$) and carotene ($p < 0.05$, $t = 2.281$) intake were significantly different.

Table 3: Mean nutrients intake (per day) of tribal preschool children of Paschamanchal of West Bengal

Nutrients intake	RDA	Sex Combined		Boys		Girls		t-value
		Mean	% of RDA	Mean	% of RDA	Mean	% of RDA	
1-3 years children (n= Sex combined-851, Boys-452, Girls-399)								
1) Energy (Kcal)	1060	695.74 (144.30)	65.63	689.87 (137.38)	65.08	702.39 (151.66)	66.26	1.264
2) Protein (gm)	16.7	14.81 (4.34)	88.68	14.81 (4.26)	88.68	14.82 (4.47)	88.74	0.0334
3) Fat (gm)	27	8.17 (3.97)	30.26	8.21 (4.15)	30.41	8.13 (3.75)	30.11	0.273
4) Carbohydrate	159	139.99	88.05	138.44	87.07	141.74	89.14	1.593

(gm)		(30.18)		(28.65)		(31.77)		
5) Calcium (mg)	600	141.97 (88.50)	23.66	143.35 (89.18)	23.89	140.41 (87.82)	23.40	-0.483
6) Iron (mg)	09	4.86 (1.38)	54	4.82 (1.37)	53.56	4.91 (1.41)	54.56	0.943
7) Zinc (mg)	05	2.70 (1.17)	54	2.70 (1.17)	54	2.69 (1.17)	53.8	0.943
8) Carotene (µg)	3200	951.27 (456.92)	29.73	937.36 (454.74)	29.29	967.03 (29.03)	30.22	1.301
9) Vita-B ₂ (mg)	0.6	0.21 (0.09)	35	0.21 (0.09)	35	0.21 (0.09)	35	0.000
10) Vita- B ₉	80	45.51 (15.40)	56.89	51.17 (14.84)	63.96	46.74 (15.99)	58.43	4.190* **
4-5 years children (n=Sex combined-356, Boys-166, Girls-190)								
1) Energy (Kcal)	1350	863.19 (90.68)	63.94	885.55 (89.19)	65.60	869.61 (91.72)	64.42	-1.657
2) Protein (gm)	20.1	18.96 (4.31)	94.33	18.88 (4.57)	93.93	19.02 (4.09)	94.63	0.307
3) Fat (gm)	25	9.72 (4.05)	38.88	9.52 (3.80)	38.08	9.89 (4.25)	39.56	0.861
4) Carbohydrate (gm)*	202	174.02 (18.35)	86.15	172.74 (18.05)	85.51	175.14 (18.58)	86.70	1.232
5) Calcium (mg)	600	200.73 (103.34)	33.46	191.39 (97.15)	31.90	208.89 (108.06)	34.82	1.597
6) Iron (mg)	13	6.59	50.69	6.41	49.31	6.75	51.92	2.304*

		(1.40)		(1.25)		(1.50)		
7) Zinc (mg)	07	3.26 (1.05)	46.5	3.24 (1.07)	46.29	3.28 (1.03)	46.86	0.359
8) Carotene (µg)	3200	1410.02 (607.80)	44.06	1331.86 (536.45)	41.62	1478.30 (657.72)	46.20	2.281*
9) Vita-B ₂ (mg)	0.8	0.28 (0.10)	35	0.27 (0.10)	33.78	0.29 (0.10)	36.25	1.883
10) Vita- B ₉ (mg)	100	63.78 (16.22)	63.8	62.23 (14.57)	62.23	65.15 (17.48)	65.15	1.698

Significant Level * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$

* A balanced diet for children is recommended to get 60% of total energy from carbohydrates.

* RDA source, A report of the Expert Group of the Indian Council of Medical Research, 2010 Nutrient Requirements and Recommended dietary allowances for Indian, ICMR.

3.5. Relationship between undernutrition and food groups intake

In present study found the relation between food group intake and different terms of undernutrition. There was no significant ($p < 0.05$) association between underweight and different food stuffs intake except green leafy vegetable ($p < 0.05$) intake, but food stuffs intake was higher (except cereals, roots and tubers, other vegetables and fruits) in normal children than in underweight children. Moreover, significant associated was cereals ($p < 0.001$), roots and tubers ($p < 0.01$) and sugar ($p < 0.01$) with stunting. On the other hand, food stuffs intake was higher (except pulses and fruits) in normal children than in stunted children. There was no significant difference between food stuffs intake and wasting except cereals ($p < 0.01$) and roots and tubers ($p < 0.01$).

3.6. Relationship between undernutrition and nutrients intake

Similarly present study also found the relationship between undernutrition and nutrients intake. It can be said that there was no significant ($p = < 0.05$) association between underweight and nutrients intake. But mean nutrients intake was higher in normal children than underweight

children. In term of stunting significant association was found with energy ($p<0.001$), carbohydrate ($p<0.001$), calcium ($p<0.01$), iron ($p<0.001$), carotene ($p<0.05$) and vitamin B₉ intake. However all nutrients intake was higher in normal children than stunted children. There was no significant association between wasting with mean nutrients intake except carbohydrate ($p<0.01$) and iron ($p<0.05$).

4. Discussion

It can be seen from the present study, intake of all food stuffs except cereals was low as per ICMR RDA in both age groups. The staple food of the people in this area was rice and bread, most of which they received through rations. A special dietary pattern can be observed in the diet of adults including children in this region. They eat rice cooked the previous day in the morning or fan rice cooked that morning with fried vegetables or boiled potato. Most of the studied children did not consume fish/meat and eggs but children in this region consumed meat from various animals hunted from the forest (rabbit, rat, forest chicken etc) as well as eggs provided by ICDS. In both 1-3 years and 4-5 years of the present study, intake of milk and fruit was lowest. The sources of milk and fruits were domesticated animals and forest fruits (Kend, Mahul, Kula, Mango, Guava etc.).

Children are vulnerable to certain major (energy, protein and fat) nutrients and various micronutrients. This is because during this period their growth rate is very high and they suffer from various infectious diseases like diarrhea and respiratory tract infections at high rate (15-18). As a result, nutrient absorption and appetite decrease and adverse metabolic disturbances occur. Therefore, if a balanced diet is not provided according to their needs during this period, their health will deteriorate (19). Steyn (2006) told that during this period it is recommended to keep enough meat, poultry, egg, fish, fruits and vegetables in the diet of preschool children (20). The food consumption patterns differ from region to region and community to community (21). In various studies in India, like present study it can be seen that the diets of tribal pre-school children were high in carbohydrate rich food such as rice, puffed rice, wheat, potatoes and protein, minerals and vitamins rich food such as meats, poultry, fish, milk, fruits were low (22-24).

Table 4: Comparison of mean nutrients (per day) intake of the tribal preschool children with other studies.

Study area and age groups		Nutrients										References
Study area	Age in Years	Energy (Kcal)	Carbohydrate (gm)	Protein (gm)	Fat (gm)	Calcium (mg)	Iron (mg)	B-carotene (mcg)	Vitamin B9 (mg)	Vitamin B2 (mg)	Zinc (mg)	
1-3 years of studied children with other studies												
Sarguja, Bihar, Tribal	1-3	801	-	22	-	122	10.5	249	-	0.29	-	Rao et al, 1994
Bihar, Tribes	1-3	980	-	28	11	212	8	510	-	0.37	-	Yadav et al, 1999
India, tribes	1-3	675	-	16.8	-	95	3.8	119.2	-	0.2.	-	Meshram et al, 2012
West Bengal, Lodha	1-3	736.71	126.5	15.8	13.8	307.9	6.19	1113.1	-	0.61	2.87	Sabud et al, 2020
ICMR RDA	1-3	1060	159*	16.7	27	600	09	3200	80	0.6	05	ICMR, 2010
Paschimanchal	1-3	695.74	139.99	14.81	8.17	141.97	8.86	951.27	45.51	0.21	2.70	Present Study
4-5 years of studied children with other studies												
Sarguja,	4-6	1421	-	37	-	181	17.1	287	-	0.48	-	Rao et al, 1994

Bihar, Tribal												
Bihar, Tribes	4-6	1328	-	38	13	237	12	591	-	0.49	-	Yadav et al, 1999
India, tribes	4-6	1002	-	25.4	-	132	5.8	195	-	0.30	-	Meshram et al, 2012
Odisha	1-5	744	-	16.7	4.4	156.5	4.3	260.8	23.8	0.20	-	Meshram et al, 2014
Kenya	36-59	1634.39	-	17.85	-	484.74	10.03	-	-	1.11	11.70	Chea et al, 2016
Punjab	4-6	796.8	104.5	28.3	27.2	285.5	6.4	292.1	74.1	0.7	2.4	Kaur et al, 2016
Punjab	3-6	533	-	14.3	-	128.2	3.15	278	39.53	0.22	1.82	Arora et al, 2016
China and Hong Kong	2.5-5	996	-	43	33	429	7.5	436	252	-	5.4	Volger et al, 2017
West Bengal, Lodha	4-5	1058.58	214.2	18.00	17.84	120.6	9.76	1403.2	-	0.78	5.22	Sabud et al, 2020
Samastipur, Bihar	3-6	1264.85	-	39.64	36.29	561.42	18.15	-	-	-	-	Kumari et al, 2020
Taiwan	3-6	760	105	29	25	162	5.3	1428	-	0.36	-	Yen et al, 2021
Jhadol, Udaipur, Rajasthan	4-5	585.18	102.98	16.98	16.99	114.06	5.15	1.4	-	-	2.34	Auddy et al, 2021

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Kotra, Udaipur, Rajasthan	4-5	682.84	117.13	20.36	17.82	99.66	6.30	12.16	-	-	0.16	Auddy et al, 2021
ICMR, RDA	4-6	1350	202.5*	20.1	25	600	13	3200	100	0.8	7	ICMR, 2010
Paschimanchal,	4-5	863.19	174.02	18.96	9.72	200.73	6.59	1410.02	63.78	0.28	3.26	Present study

In children aged 1-3 years, intake of each nutrient and energy in the present study was lower as per ICMR approved RDA (12). Carbohydrate and protein intakes of children in this age group were not significantly lower than the RDA, but intakes of energy, fat, calcium, beta-carotene, folic acid, vitamin B2 and zinc were significantly lower. Another study in this area shows that Lodha children aged 1–3-year-old had lower intake of dietary fat, calcium, beta carotene and vitamin B2 than all other studied children (25). In another Indian tribal study, children aged 1-3 years had the lowest dietary intake of energy, calcium, iron, beta-carotene and vitamin B2 (26). Similarly, the intake of all nutrients among children aged 4–5-year-old in the present study was lower than the ICMR recommended RDA. The findings from national and international studies are presented in Table 4 for comparison.

5. Conclusion

The findings of this study indicate that undernutrition remains a significant public health concern among tribal preschool children in the Paschimanchal area and is closely associated with food insecurity and nutrient deficiencies. The high prevalence of stunting (chronic undernutrition), and underweight, reflects both long-term and immediate nutritional deprivation. Consequently, reducing the burden of underweight requires not only ensuring adequate nutrient intake among children but also enhancing maternal awareness and knowledge regarding appropriate child feeding and nutrition practices.

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Conflict of Interest: There is no conflict of interest.

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